

COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article explores the cognitive activity of students in the context of digitalization of education. The development of information and communication technologies has significantly influenced the ways of obtaining, processing and using information in the educational process. The changes in the motivational sphere, goals, methods and results of students' cognitive activity related to the accessibility and ease of information retrieval are analyzed. The influence of digitalization on the perception, processing and use of information is considered, as well as the need for the formation of competencies for the successful application of acquired knowledge in solving practical problems.*

Keywords: *cognitive activity, students, digitalization of education, information and communication technologies, motivation, goals, methods, results, accessibility of information, perception, processing, use, competencies.*

In modern society, specialists who show interest and desire for continuous training are valued. The ability to be an active subject in the process of cognitive activity at all stages of professional growth is formed while studying at a higher educational institution. In the conditions of digitalization of the socio-cultural environment, an urgent problem of full and harmonious personal development arises. In this context, a special role is played by the sphere of education and higher education as an important institution of socialization and formation of the future generation[2].

From a psychological and pedagogical perspective, the development of students' personal potential depends on the creation of suitable conditions that contribute to successful self-realization in the learning process [7]. It is important to take into account that students have various abilities and internal resources that can be revealed and developed during their studies, consolidation and subsequent growth, especially important for their personal and professional development. Thus, it is necessary to create a stimulating pedagogical environment that will allow students to unlock their potential and successfully realize their self-realization.

The category "cognition" reflects the procedural nature of the activity associated with cognitive activity, which consists in reflecting and reproducing reality in thinking. In the course of cognition, we master the sensory information that we perceive or experience in order to achieve the truth. This interaction between the cognizing subject and the object leads to the formation of new knowledge [6].

In the process of cognitive activity, various mental processes are used, such as sensation, perception, attention, representation, memory, thinking, imagination and speech. At its core, cognition is a mental process that allows a person to receive and assimilate knowledge.

Analyzing students as a unique social category, a specific community of people united by the Institute of Higher Education, I.A. Zimnaya identifies the key features of student age: high

level of education, high motivation to learn, active participation in public life and a harmonious combination of intellectual and social maturity [3].

Modern features of students' cognitive activity are associated with their increasingly active participation in educational processes due to the development of information and communication technologies. According to the theory of generations by N. Howe and V. Strauss, for generation Y (millennials born in 1983-2000) and generation Z (centenials born in 2001-2020), such active involvement corresponds to their characteristics and needs [5].

Modern methods of communication are mainly carried out through social networks, and the development of new devices takes place independently and almost intuitively, without the need for instructions. Generation Z grows up early, and some of them successfully implement their business ideas already at school age. The main expectations of this generation from the future are connected with comfort and tranquility [3].

Modern students face one of the main features of cognitive activity - they work in conditions of full availability of various information and ease of its search. This affects their motivation, goals, methods and results in the process of cognition. On the one hand, the availability of information and its easy acquisition expand the opportunities for knowledge accumulation: students have access to electronic libraries, databases, can participate in webinars and conferences, communicate with leading scientists, etc. However, as A.A. notes. Golovanova, such ease of access to information can lead to a decrease in the value of the knowledge that students possess. The question arises, why make efforts for effective memorization, repetition and intellectual stress, if you can always just "Google" in a search engine? [1].

It is obvious that only students who are motivated and understand the difference between information and knowledge, as well as understand the importance of knowledge for their future professional activities and careers, will choose the traditional path of knowledge, which includes the stages of "perception-comprehension-memorization-application". For students with low academic motivation, this path is replaced by the strategy of "finding", "copying", "saving (to some medium)". The development of non-cognitive skills, such as digital literacy, information and communication competence, emotional and social intelligence, etc., is certainly important. However, unfortunately, this is a reproductive form of thinking and imagination.

In Russian science, the study of the problem of personal potential is based on traditional scientific concepts, such as the activity approach (presented by S.L. Rubinstein and A.N. Leontiev) and the cultural-historical theory of the development of higher mental functions (formulated by L.S. Vygotsky). Within the framework of these concepts, personal potential is considered as the ability of a person to become an active and capable subject, which she acquires in the process of socialization and assimilation of socio-cultural experience [9].

Foreign research in the field of personal potential has largely been formed under the influence of humanistic psychology, which is a third force opposed to psychoanalysis and behaviorism. This direction inspired the movement for the development of human potential of researchers such as G. Allport, K. Rogers and A. Maslow. Within the framework of this approach, personal potential and its realization are considered as a feature of a fully functioning personality according to K. Rogers. The action of this potential is usually associated with manifestations of Self as an internal source of activity in the process of self-realization. The self, being a system of stable ideas about itself, reproduces this system in behavior and acts as an internal program that

reveals the inherent dominants in it. In this approach, it is possible to detect a hidden preformist interpretation of personal potential, which is also inherent in other foreign approaches to varying degrees. For example, in the theory of autopoiesis, U. Maturan and F. Varely, the problem of personal potential is explained through the self-reproduction of a person due to the "autopoietic organization" of his own nature. The preformist approach is also largely present in cognitive, Gestaltist and other teachings.

These and other approaches are of great importance for creating an educational environment that promotes personal development. In the context of the intensive development of digital technologies in the field of education, especially in the higher education system, there is a need to study the possibilities and features of the use of modern information and communication technologies in order to develop the personal potential of modern students.

Some authors talk about the inevitable risks that accompany the process of digitalization of education. In such a situation, it becomes obvious that pedagogical, psychological and medical research on issues related to the digitalization of education is not carried out enough, and there are no scientific programs aimed at purposeful and comprehensive study of this area, as well as analysis of foreign experience [8].

Given the multifaceted nature of the problem of digitalization of education and the importance of all its components, let's summarize the psychological risks associated with the cognitive development of students in digital education. So, according to I.M. Osmolovskaya, new aspects of the pedagogical process are connected:

1 with changes in the psychology of perception, processing and use of information by students;

2 with full involvement of learning in the information space;

3 with learning motivation problems when the old incentives stop working;

4 with the need to form effective knowledge among students - knowledge that is not just stored in memory, but successfully applied in practical situations. In the field of didactics, this is due to the development of competence - the ability of students to apply the acquired knowledge to solve various types of problems [4].

Thus, summarizing the above, we note that in the context of higher education, a representative of generation Z is a typical subject of cognitive activity. They are characterized by a special interaction with information both in format and content, which affects the motivational, target, operational and resultant aspects of the cognitive process in the context of digitalization of education. The change in the system of interaction between personality and information has led to the fact that access to information has become a priority, rather than its full possession.

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